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A MODEL FOR TIME-INDEPENDENT AND TIME-DEPENDENT DAMAGE EVOLUTION AND ITS INFLUENCE ON CREEP OF MULTIDIRECTIONAL POLYMER COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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Abstract

Time-independent and time-dependent damage (TID and TDD) in multidirectional polymer composite laminates develop during manufacturing due to process-induced residual stress as well as during quasi-static loading and creep loading, degrading its modulus and strength. A model to predict both time-independent and time-dependent transverse cracking in multiple plies of a multidirectional polymer composite laminate is presented. The stress state in the intact regions of the plies are determined using the lamination theory and incremental loading to the desired load. The stored elastic energy, determined using this stress state, is compared with a critical value for failure to determine if a ply would fail after the increment. If failure is predicted, variational analysis is used to determine the perturbation in ply stresses due to cracking and the crack density. The new stress state is used to determine the laminate modulus after cracking and the ply stress after next increment. This procedure is repeated to determine the crack evolution and the degradation in modulus. Model predictions compare very well with experimental results for a $[\pm\theta_m/90_n]_s$ laminate.

1 Introduction

Polymer matrix composites exhibit time-dependent degradation in modulus (creep) and strength (creep rupture) due to the viscoelasticity of the polymer matrix. Additional contribution comes from various damage modes that evolve with time in polymer composite laminates, such as transverse cracking, vertical cracking, delamination, as well as interaction among them. These damage modes can develop during curing and cool-down process from the curing temperature to room temperature as well

as quasi-static loading to the creep load, known as Time-Independent Damage (TID) and with time under constant creep load known as Time-Dependent Damage (TDD). These damage modes evolve in multiple plies sequentially as well as simultaneously depending on the loading conditions, temperature and stacking sequence. Evolution of TID and TDD influences the creep and creep rupture of polymer composites. Published research (both experimental and theoretical) on TID and its effect on modulus of composite is extensive [1-40]. While these have focused on a single damage mode in a single ply group, few studies have focused on multiple TID damage modes [2, 3, 12, 17, 33]. While there are few studies on the effect of single mode of damage on creep [41, 43-48], there are no studies modeling of TID and TDD evolution in multiple plies and the impact of both TID and TDD on creep and creep rupture of multidirectional polymer composite laminates.

In this paper, an analytical model based on variational analysis along with critical stored elastic energy as the failure criterion has been developed to predict the simultaneous evolution of TID and TDD in multiple plies and their influence on creep of multidirectional polymer composite laminates. Only one damage mode, i.e. transverse cracking, has been focused in this paper.

2 Model

The developed model is comprehensive and considers the three zone of process and load history identified in Fig. 1. A block diagram of the developed creep model is provided in Fig. 2 and it consists of four integrated modules. The Process-Induced Stress (PIS) module predicts the ply stress

state for an imposed process history. The Quasi-Static Load (QSL) module predicts the stress state for an imposed load profile with initial values input from PSI module. The Static Load (SL) module predicts the stress state as a function of time during creep with initial values input from QSL module. All these modules use lamination theory to predict the stress state in the plies during each incremental change in the variable relevant for a given zone, indicated in Fig. 1. Incremental change in temperature (ΔT), load ($\Delta\sigma$), and time (Δt) are the variables corresponding to PSI, QSL, and SL modules, respectively. This incremental analysis is required to take into account the change in material properties with the change in the magnitude of identified variables as well as perturbation in stresses due to TID and TDD. During each incremental step, each of these modules will determine the stored elastic energy and compare it with a critical energy limit to predict if a ply would fracture during that step. The critical stored elastic energy for fracture for each ply of the laminate was determined using unidirectional composites, applying the model and the approach developed by Raghavan and Meshii [49]. If a fracture is not predicted, the variable is changed by a pre-determined magnitude and the simulation procedure is repeated. If failure is predicted, a fourth Variational Analysis (VA) module, shown in Fig. 2, is accessed. This module is the core of this creep model and predicts perturbation in the stress state of a ply due to cracking as well as the new crack density, which would be input to the module that invoked the VA module. Using this data, the module that predicted fracture recalculates the average stress state in the plies of the laminates, average stress and strain on the laminate, and modulus / compliance of the laminate. These along with crack density are output by the PIS, QSL, and SL modules as a function of simulation variables used in those modules.

2.1 Variational Analysis (VA) Module

When a crack occurs in one ply, the stress state in all plies of the laminate will be altered. The main goal of the variational analysis is to determine an admissible stress state that satisfies the equilibrium equations, interface continuity conditions, and traction boundary conditions. Consider a $[\theta_m/90_n]_s$ laminate that has developed a crack density of $\lambda^{(90)}$,

$\lambda^{(-\theta)}$, and $\lambda^{(+\theta)}$ in $[90]$, $[-\theta]$, and $[\theta]$ plies respectively, as shown in Fig. 3, in response to a uniaxial stress (σ_{xx}) applied parallel to the longitudinal axis of the laminate. The crack density $\lambda^{(k)}$ is equal to $1/(2a^{(k)})$, as shown in Fig. 3. t_{h_k} is the thickness of each ply, and h_1 and h_2 are the distance of the top surfaces of $[-\theta]$ and $[\theta]$ plies from the symmetry line. Since crack density in various plies is not the same at any given stress, the entire gage length of the laminate, shown in Fig. 3 is used in modeling. When there is no crack, the plies of the laminate are in plane stress condition stresses in the plies are determined using the lamination theory. Let a new crack forms in a ply (e.g., $[90]$) of $[\theta_m/90_n]_s$ laminate during an applied stress increment, $\Delta\sigma$, from $\sigma_{xx,i-1}$ to $\sigma_{xx,i}$. The stress distribution among the plies would change and a three dimensional state of stress would be introduced. The new stress state in each ply at applied stress is given by

$$\sigma_{xx,i}^{(k)}(x) = \sigma_{xx,i-1}^{(k)} - \sigma_{xx}^{P(k)}(x) = \sigma_{xx,i-1}^{(k)} - \varphi^{(k)}(x) \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_{xy,i}^{(k)}(x) = \sigma_{xy,i-1}^{(k)} - \sigma_{xy}^{P(k)}(x) = \sigma_{xy,i-1}^{(k)} - \psi^{(k)}(x) \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_{yy,i}^{(k)}(x) = \sigma_{yy,i-1}^{(k)} - \sigma_{yy}^{P(k)}(x) = \sigma_{yy,i-1}^{(k)} - \eta^{(k)}(x) \quad (3)$$

where $\varphi^{(k)}(x)$, $\psi^{(k)}(x)$, and $\eta^{(k)}(x)$ are the axial, transverse, and shear perturbation stresses for ply (k) , respectively.

Substituting the general form of stress distribution given by Eq. (1)-(3) into equilibrium equations and applying the appropriate boundary conditions, equations for the stress state in each ply are obtained. Then, the obtained stress state contains three unknown perturbation stresses (i.e., $\varphi^{(k)}(x)$, $\psi^{(k)}(x)$ and $\eta^{(k)}(x)$) for each layer (total of nine unknowns) were input to the complementary energy integral. In order to determine these perturbation stresses, the *principle of minimum complementary energy* is applied. The Euler-Lagrange equations were derived by first variation of each complementary energy functional with respect to each perturbation term. These differential equations were solved using MATLAB *bvp4c* function and applying imposed boundary condition of constant strain rate. Additional details can be found in Ref. [50].

3 Experimental and Simulation Details

[±45/90₂]_s composite laminates, consisting of F263-7 epoxy resin reinforced with Toho G30-500 carbon fiber, were manufactured using a prescribed autoclave cure cycle and used to prepare the tensile test coupons. Repetitive tensile tests were used to record time-independent evolution of transverse crack density in multiple plies with increase in applied stress at 80°C and 180°C. Creep tests were also carried out in these two temperatures for four stress levels to record the creep response and evolution of transverse cracking in multiple plies with time. Simulation details can be found in Ref. [50].

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Ply stresses Perturbations

A representative plot of the distribution in axial perturbation stress (ϕ) for the three plies of the laminate, around a single crack in [90] plies predicted by the VA module at 43 MPa and 180°C, is shown in Fig. 4. For this testing condition, only [90] plies crack and the transverse crack density in [90] plies is 2.6 cm⁻¹. The perturbation in [90] plies is maximum at the crack location and decreases to zero away from the crack. The perturbation in [±45] plies is negative and increases the axial stresses in these plies. The values for $\phi^{(-45)}$ (hence, $\phi^{(-45)_{\max}}$) would be different from the values for $\phi^{(+45)}$ due to the proximity of [-45] plies to cracks in [90] plies. This is supported by the experimental data; the transverse cracking in [-45] plies started at a lower stress than that in [+45] plies.

4.2 Time-independent crack density and modulus

The predicted evolution of transverse crack density is compared with the experimental values in Fig. 5. The predicted stresses for onset of transverse cracking at 80°C are 30 MPa, 45.7 MPa, and 46.5 MPa for [90], [-45], and [+45] plies respectively. They compare very well with experimental results of 28±2 MPa, 45 ± 5 MPa, and 55±5 MPa. While the experimental TID increases gradually, the predicted TID at 80°C shows a sudden increase at ~ 40 MPa. This difference is believed to be due to the large difference between the assumed uniform crack spacing and the experimentally observed distribution in crack spacing, specifically at stresses less than ~

70 MPa. However, at stress levels above 70 MPa, when the distribution in crack spacing is narrow, the predicted crack density in [90] and [-45] plies is within experimental scatter and compares very well with experimental results at 80°C. Hence, it is believed that accounting for the distribution in crack spacing, due to stochastic nature of cracking, would improve the accuracy of prediction at low stress and crack density levels. Similarly, the predicted crack density in [+45] plies at 80°C is within the experimental scatter at stress levels > 80 MPa. The observed difference at lower stress levels is believed to be due to the assumption of uniform crack spacing as well as onset of other damage modes beyond 65± 5 MPa, which are not considered in the model. Similar results were obtained at higher temperatures.

The predicted modulus is well within the scatter range of experimental results, as shown in Fig. 6. The predicted rate of degradation in modulus with increase in applied stress compares very well with experimental results at stress levels below ~80 MPa when only transverse cracking of plies is observed.

4.3 Time-dependent crack density, laminate stress, strain, and modulus

Fig. 7 shows the time-dependent evolution of stored elastic energy in plies determined using the time-dependent predicated stresses and strains. The predicted evolution of the transverse crack density with time, in multiple plies of [±45/90₂]_s, are plotted and compared with experimental results in Fig. 8 for a creep stress of 45 MPa at 80 °C. The predicted transverse crack densities, upon loading, were 3 cm⁻¹, 0 cm⁻¹ and 0 cm⁻¹ [90], [-45] and [+45] plies, respectively, and the corresponding experimental crack densities were 1.8 cm⁻¹, 0.6 cm⁻¹ and 0.3 cm⁻¹ in [90], [-45] and [+45] plies, respectively. The simultaneous transverse cracking of [±45] plies had resulted in a lower crack density in [90] plies during experiments. However, the model predicts a higher crack density in [90] plies, with no cracking in [±45] plies upon loading to 45 MPa. The sample used in crack characterization test had process-induced cracks while no such cracking due to PIS was predicted by the model. The magnitude and the trend in crack evolution with time in [90] plies are in a good agreement with experimental results. The predicted crack density in [90] plies at a time corresponding to the end of crack characterization

tests (12.6 days) is 5.2 cm^{-1} while the experimental crack density at this time was 5.7 cm^{-1} . The crack density in [90] ply measured in the sample used for creep experiment was 6.6 cm^{-1} at a time of 7.8 days while the corresponding predicted value is 5 cm^{-1} .

The predicted magnitude and the trend in the evolution of transverse cracking in [-45] and [+45] plies are also in a good agreement with the experimental results generated by crack characterization tests. While the predicted crack density at the end of the test are 1.2 cm^{-1} and 0.6 cm^{-1} in [-45] and [+45] plies respectively, the experimental values were 1.2 cm^{-1} and 0.9 cm^{-1} . The transverse crack density values measured in the creep sample were 0.3 cm^{-1} and 0.2 cm^{-1} differed from the predicted results which are 0.3 cm^{-1} and 0.9 cm^{-1} at the day of 7.8. It is believed that the influence of cracking evolution of the plies on one another resulted in a higher crack density in [90] plies and lower crack density in [\pm 45] plies in the sample tested in creep compared to the predicted results.

4.4 Creep

The predicted creep strains of the multidirectional laminate, are compared with experimental results in Fig. 9 and Fig. 10 for two creep stress levels of 45 MPa and 54 MPa, respectively at 80°C . The process-induced thermal strain was considered in experimental results. In order to make a better comparison, the difference in the instantaneous strain (i.e. at t_0) is eliminated. Hence, the experimental and predicted curves were superposed by shifting the curves vertically by an amount equal to the difference in instantaneous. The maximum difference between the predicted creep and experimental creep strain at a time of 7.8 days corresponding to the end of creep experiment is 7.3 % at 45 MPa and time of 10.4 days is 11.8 % at 54 MPa. In order to highlight the contribution from TDD on creep, creep strain at these stresses were also predicted without allowing the plies to crack. These predictions without TDD, plotted in Fig. 9 and Fig. 10, clearly demonstrate the role played by TDD on creep. Similar results were obtained at higher temperatures.

Conclusion

A model, integrating lamination theory and variational analysis, has been developed to predict simultaneous time-independent followed by time-dependent evolution of transverse cracking in multiple plies of a multi-directional polymer composite laminate and its effect on laminate creep. The model predictions for time-independent transverse cracking in a [\pm 45/90]_s laminate compare very well with experimental results, for time-dependent and time-independent evolution of transverse crack density, laminate modulus and creep compliance, validating the model. Further improvements to the model, by accounting for the additional damage modes and eliminating the assumptions such as constant crack spacing, constancy of perturbation stress along the thickness and width of the plies, and location of cracks in [+45] plies, are likely to increase the prediction accuracy of the model.

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Fig. 1. Process and load history considered in the model

Fig.2. Creep Model

Fig. 3: $[\pm\theta_m/90_n]_s$ with damage in various plies

Fig. 4. Distribution of axial perturbation stresses between two transverse cracks in [90] plies of $[\pm 45/90_2]_s$ at 43 MPa and 180°C

Fig. 5. Evolution of TID in various plies of $[\pm 45/90_2]_s$ at 80 °C and

Fig. 6. Experimental and predicted modulus degradation during quasi-static loading of $[\pm 45/90_2]_s$ laminate at 80°C and

Fig. 7. Evolution of stored elastic energy with time in various plies of $[\pm 45/90_2]_s$ at 80°C and 45 MPa

Fig. 9. Comparison of experimental and predicted evolution of transverse crack density with time in multiple plies of $[\pm 45/90_2]_s$ at 80°C and 45 MPa

Fig. 11. Comparison of predicted strain with total experimental strain after eliminating the difference at t_0 for 54 MPa and 80°C

Fig. 10. Comparison of predicted strain with total experimental strain, after eliminating the difference at t_0 for 45 MPa and 80°C